

Total Quality Management and Performance of Adventist Elementary Schools

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the Total Quality Management of Adventist education in North- Central Mindanao Conference in school year 2016-2017. It covered the 20 Adventist schools of Bukidnon. 124 Adventist Elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study.

TQM quality indicators include: access; services to customers; leadership; physical environment and resources; effective learning and teaching; students; staff; external relations; organizations; and standards. School performance was based on the annual evaluation done by the Education Department of North-Central Mindanao Conference. The study utilized the descriptive – correlational design. A survey questionnaire was used to gather reliable data from the respective schools.

Most of the teachers have an age range of 26-35 years old. Majority of them are married and bachelor degree holders. Almost half of them worked for 3 years and below.

The level of Total Quality Management implementation among Adventist schools in Bukidnon is “moderately implemented”.

The school performance rating of the Adventist schools in Bukidnon is Very Satisfactory.

The null hypothesis 1 is accepted since there is no significant relationship between the variables.

There is a significant difference of student variable and school performance, thus, null hypothesis is rejected.

In TQM implementation, several indicators’ needs to be implemented in all Adventist schools. Quality tools and techniques to improve the school must be established so that continuous quality checking can be done so that indicators that needs improvement will be developed and addressed positively.

CHAPTER 1

A. INTRODUCTION

Total quality management is a philosophy that necessitates the continuous development, progress, and change of numerous students in training. It is essential to convey productivity to each measurement, whether it is displaying learning educational programs or a foundation.

Toremén et al 2009 identify the need for a compelling change in management by instructing staff and utilizing human resources to achieve a framework-wide quality change in order to actualize total quality management standards in a general sense TQM endeavors at primary schools are critical to accomplishing a superb education framework quality ought to be the embodiment of the training framework so that different fields will enable progress and get different kinds of help from the education system school education is the establishment or building block for advanced education in the event that we do not pay consideration to the quality of instruction at the school level the training and mission of proficiency will be a failure without total quality management it will be difficult for us to push forward shoulder to shoulder other educational organizations works an education system worldwide the establishments of this system are joined by one basic philosophy this fundamental point of view is mirrored in every classroom school program and activity that reflects this fundamental point of view the Adventist philosophy of instruction is Christ-focused and under the direction of the blessed soul gods character and purposes can be comprehended as uncovered in the book of scriptures in Jesus Christ and in nature the unmistakable characteristics of Adventist education derived from the book of scriptures and Ellen G. Whites' works point to the redemptive point of genuine instruction to restore individuals to the image of their creator for example according to the seventh-day Adventist mission to general conference in 2010 customarily competed for fame for quality education with external estimations for example achievement levels of students and graduate success as two confirmations of that quality in a few nations while in others other performance indicators have been used in later years with an expanded emphasis on the more developmental components of achieving quality in the academic field as well as in every aspect of campus operation for organizations self-reflection all-encompassing thought of quality demands additionally reflects the churches accentuation on education that spotlights the whole this encourages administrators to use quality management structures and improvement procedures to improve education and joy for their clients on spiritual levels as well as educational social physical and emotional levels to ensure that the Adventist philosophy of education and the standards of faith and learning are incorporated into the lives of each of their students in its schools around the globe an education department was set up at all levels of the churches managerial system working intimately with the education officers of the world consisting of 13 divisions of the Adventist church operating schools in 145 nations the staff at the corporate world headquarters guarantees the quality of the worldwide Adventist education system general conference in 2010 one of the elements of the education department to organize accreditation Adventist institutions managed by accrediting team schools accrediting association satisfies this duty and distinguishes in its handbook its desires for institutional operation this will help administrators upgrade institutional quality as per the Adventist accrediting associations desires and global best practice the total quality approach continually inspects the way things are done and searches for approaches to enhance procedures and frameworks keeping in mind the end goal of getting better results it starts with the conviction frameworks of those gatherings connecting with each other in the classroom the two primary gatherings included are educators and students one of the elements of the education department of the organize the accreditation of all Adventist managed by the seventh-day Adventist accrediting team schools accrediting association satisfies duty and distinguishes in its handbook its desires for institutional operation this will help administrators upgrade institutional quality as per the Adventist accrediting associations desires and global best practice the total quality approach continually inspects the way things are done and searches for approaches to enhance procedures and frameworks keeping in mind the end goal of getting better results it starts with the conviction frameworks of those gatherings connecting with each other in the classroom the two primary gatherings included are educators and students on the other hand if a teacher approaches a class and believes that each has been given a unique gift to learn that each has hidden

capacities yet to be discovered and that each is a potential possibility for gods kingdom there will be a different classroom atmosphere and the class accomplishment levels will rise on the other hand if an educator believes that students are unequipped to accomplish anything each lesson movement or program will be designed to demoralize students the quality approach works since it energizes teamwork and coordinated effort it empowers everybody in the classroom to identify insufficient procedures and systems and to suggest changes in investigating and actualizing the researcher hopes to determine how the Adventist schools provide services to their students meanwhile they are looking into ways to improve their management systems with the goal of increasing effectiveness and quality and determining school performance among Adventist schools in northern Mindanao.

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Total quality management is a philosophy that demands advancement, change, and a considerable number of students in training. It needs to convey productivity to each measurement, whether it is showing learning programs or foundation. Toremén et al 2009 recognize the need for a compelling change by training employees and utilizing human resources to actualize this general sense a framework-wide change is required. Primary school tqm efforts are critical to achieving a superior framework.

School education is the establishment or building block for advanced education. In the event that we do not pay consideration to the quality of instruction at the school level, the training and mission of proficiency will be a failure, pushing forward organizations shoulder to shoulder. Seventh-day collaborative educational institutions all over the world the foundations of this system are linked by a common philosophy. This fundamental point of view is mirrored in every classroom, school program, and activity that reflects this point of view. Christ-focused and direction blessed soul gods comprehended uncovered in the book of scriptures. An unmistakable education derived Ellen G. White's points to the genuine instruction in restoring people to their creator image by encouraging, throughout their individual advancement, students to a useful and enjoyable life.

For example, the 2010 brought up two customarily competing external estimations, for example, achievement levels and success as two confirmations of that quality nation. In others, other performance indicators have been used in later years. This all-encompassing thought demands that we additionally reflect on the church's emphasis on spotlights. This encourages administrators to use management structures and improvement procedures to improve education and joy for their clients on spiritual levels as well as social, physical, and emotional standards incorporated into their schools. They work intimately with officers consisting of churches operating schools in 145 nations.

One of the elements of the education department of the general conference is to organize the accreditation of all Adventist institutions managed by the seventh-day Adventist church the accrediting team of seventh-day Adventist schools Accrediting Association satisfies this duty and distinguishes in its handbook its desires for institutional operation this will help administrators upgrade institutional quality as per the Adventist accrediting associations desires and global best practice the total quality approach continually inspects the way things are done and searches for approaches to enhance procedures and frameworks keeping in mind the end goal of getting better results it starts with the conviction frameworks of

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B. Statement of the Problem

The primary goal of the study was to assess Total Quality Management implementation and Performance of Adventist Elementary School in Bukidnon in the S.Y 2016-2017. This will specifically answer the following questions:

- a) What is the profile of the Adventist teachers in terms of:
 - a. age;
 - b. gender;
 - c. civil status;
 - d. educational attainment; and
 - e. years in service?

- b) What is the level of Total Quality Management implementation in terms of:
 - a. access;
 - b. services to customers;
 - c. leadership;
 - d. physical environment and resources;
 - e. effective learning and teaching;
 - f. students;
 - g. staff;
 - h. external relations;
 - i. organizations; and
 - j. standards?

- c) What is the school performance of the Adventist schools?

- d) Is there a significant relationship between the profile and level of TQM implementation and school performance in Adventist education?

- e) Is there a significant difference between the level of implementation of TQM and school performance in Adventist education?

C. Research Hypothesis

Based on the conceptual framework and problem of the study, the hypothesis formulated below will be subjected for testing within the 0.05 level of significance:

- a) There is no significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and level of Total quality management towards the school performance.
- b) There is no significant difference between the TQM and school performance.

D. Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The research determined the total quality management of Adventist education in the North-Central Mindanao Conference during the 2016-2017 school years. It encompassed Bukidnon's Adventist schools.

The study's participants were Adventist Elementary School teachers.

Access, customer service, leadership, physical environment and resources, effective learning and teaching, students, staff, external relations, organizations, and standards are all quality indicators in TQM.

School performance was based on the annual evaluation done by the Education Department of the North-Central Mindanao Conference.

E. Significance of the Study

Findings of the study would specifically be addressed for benefit of the following individuals and sectors.

Administrators the findings of the study will help executives see how to utilize fundamental tools it will also permit those in the organization to assume liability for the procedures they manage tqm will enable administrators to comprehend and persistently enhance the procedures they oversee this will empower them to conjecture the conceivable achievement and failure lines over the span of the organizations operations subsequently helping the organization to accomplish the breakthrough process change.

Head principals the head principals will be guided on the principles that are viable in enhancing school performance with the utilization of the tqm the study will be valuable to the assurance office and different prevailing authorities in arranging strategy making in addition the principals and teachers of Adventist schools will be educated about the difficulties confronted by their institution and they will have the capacity to discover suitable and conceivable answers to these difficulties guaranteeing viable tqm implementation.

Teachers/staff presence and practical usage of tqm will give scene to teachers to adjust themselves in the class of the exceptionally globalize environment the study will help teachers to exploit their possibilities to the fullest conceivable approaches to being sufficiently cognizant in working with quality and delivering quality outputs awareness of teachers on the significance of tqm help them turn out to be more motivated obviously to hasten their workability to expand proficiency and effectiveness level of the organization.

Students'/parents' improvement of services towards the students staff parents and other stakeholders will be expected by identifying the areas that need improvement better provision of services will be enhanced through the findings of the study.

Education department NCMC the results of the study will be useful for policymakers know the difficulties confronting the implementation of tqm in Adventist schools along these lines they will have the capacity to devise conceivable answers for difficulties while making policies NCMC needs to effectively accomplish its objective of upgrading the results of the study will give gauge information to account on the organizational quality Adventist findings can likewise be utilized as a measure as a part of deciding organizational capacity of the Adventist schools which are beneficiaries of accreditation the result of the study will give benchmark circumstance of the Adventist school of NCMC as far as tqm practices quality indicators can portray the qualities and shortcoming Adventist.

Accreditations wide utilization management frameworks makes read competitiveness in Adventist implementation total quality management in Adventist educational will interact with group results will help the organizations to satisfy the prerequisites and be set up the assessment every Adventist schools.

CHAPTER 2

A. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter discusses the related literature and studies that provide direct reference in conceptualizing the research study.

The Seventh-day Adventist church has made a promise to giving an expansive education and spiritual arrangement for kids, youth and youthful grown-ups inside the setting of the Christian perspective. Seventh-day Adventist, inside the setting of their essential convictions, recognize that God is the maker and sustainer of the whole universe; quicken and lifeless. He made impeccable people in his own particular image with power to think, to choose, and to do (Rao, 2008).

Rao (2009) avows that Adventist education grants more than academic learning. It cultivates an adjusted improvement of the entire individual spiritually, mentally, physically, and socially. Students finishing the optional level at an Adventist school ought to have had a chance to submit their lives to God and in this manner show a developing faith in Him, described by individual dedication, open worship, and a service and observer to others in satisfaction of the churches' central goal.

As indicated by White (1995), "teachers for Adventist schools ought to be chosen from the absolute best class. They ought to be experienced Christians who are adjusted and balanced in mind, men and women who have taken in the lesson of discretion" (pp. 95, 96). "They ought to instruct and take the necessary steps of higher significance than even the minister in lecturing the word. They can set up the soil that the truth may have impact upon human hearts" (pp.237, 238)

It is faith, world view, and beliefs that engender philosophy and values. The philosophy and values interact with one another and thus produce attitudes. These attitudes are the foundation for Adventist behavior and relationship between a teacher and students in a classroom. That is, it is the attitude that will influence teacher's thought and language in the classroom (Kang,2013).The kind and loving attitude will assist students through their difficulties rather than criticizing them, being harsh or rough to them. Through love and kindness, students need the personal sharing of teachers in their lives to help them understand their choices.

Knight (2006) observes that only when teachers clearly understand their philosophy and examine its implication for daily activities in a Christian setting, they can expect to be effective in reaching their personal goals and those of the school for which they teach. Knight (2009) further explains that challenges of Adventist schools date back to the time of the Second Advent Movement of the early nineteenth century. It was in the era of institutional development that the Adventist Philosophy of education found its background.

Providing effective wholistic education is necessary in schools and is aimed at ensuring the harmonious growth and development of students to be responsible members of the society. Adequate or inadequate teacher training in Adventist education philosophy is an operational mechanism which is capable of generating both positive and negative influence over students and subsequently school's performance. Nevertheless, Espinoza, (2012) emphasizes that "educators should be conscious of the crucial role they play in students' lives.

Alobedt (2011) in his research showed that the gender of management is effective on the implementation of the quality management program effective and male managers did better than the female managers. Delkhoshksmai (2012) reported that in gender there is a significant difference between the managers' skills (male and female). Regarding the situation surrounding the leadership of the quality management component, were also reported between the performances of the managers there are differences

according to gender. Some experts also believe that a woman in the implementation of the total quality management is better than men.

In view of the status of educational degree, Delgshai findings (2004) also showed that the amount of attention to the customer in administrative managers based on degree was different. Finally, in terms of experience, in all dimensions, except the perceptual skills and leadership was seen a significant difference that this results in line with the Alobiedat research (2011).

In the study of Thakkar et al (2006) they found out that there is significant difference between male and female teachers in the perception about TQM in education. There is no significant difference between Arts and Science secondary school teachers in the perception about TQM in education. More than 50% secondary school teachers exhibited Average level of perception about TQM in education. Female teachers in secondary schools had better perception about Total Quality Management (TQM) in education than male teachers. Arts and Science teachers in secondary school do not differ in the perception about TQM in education. They concluded that educational organizations, such as schools, colleges and universities should have individuals who are committed to their organization, profession and well- being of their students. The vitality of all educational organizations lies in the willingness of principals to contribute to the development of their organizations. The process of TQM will lead to all round development of the institution, principals, teachers and students. The literature reveals that there is no difference between male and female of teachers in the level of perception total quality management in education (Temponi 2005).

In contrast, study found the significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers in the perception about TQM in education. It has been suggested that total quality management may be a more feminine style of leading, but (Ali and Zairi 2005) found a significant difference between female and male teachers and total quality management. Men attributed their use of power and direct styles to total quality management, whereas women attributed their use of relational styles to total quality management.

In examining the perception of secondary school teachers on total quality management in education, Pour and Yeshodhara (2011) revealed that more than half secondary school teachers exhibited average level of perception about TQM in education. However, the percentage of teachers with above average level of perception about TQM was more (24.3%) than that of teachers with below average level of perception about TQM (19.9%). The study revealed that there was significant difference found between male and female teachers in the perception of total quality management. Female teachers had higher mean score than male teachers.

Effective implementation of total quality management (TQM) in organizations has become an important concern to the workforce including customers, employees, professional and profitable companies who are working directly or indirectly in the organizations. TQM is a general management philosophy and a combination of different tools which compel educational institutions to follow a description of quality and the ways to attain it (Murad and Rajesh, 2010).

Total Quality Management has been accepted as a management paradigm by a lot of organizations throughout the world. Quality movement has been originated with quality improvements project at business companies throughout the world. But later this quality movement was extended to other institutions including insurance; non-profit organizations; banking; healthcare; educational institutions and government. Total quality management models based on quality education generally comprised of a number of principals or essential elements i.e., top management leadership; teamwork; workforce involvement; customer focus; continuous improvement tools, training etc. (Oduwaiye, et al., 2012).

Though educational systems are going through vigorous development and restructuring, TQM has captured the attention of educational managers and leaders who are worried to ensure educational outcomes through students' achievement (Siu-Runyan and Heart, 2012). Quality of education is an important issue in

the world of competitive environment. Therefore, changes or amendments are required in the educational process to improve education (Mishra and Pandey, 2013).

Education is an indispensable requirement for the national growth and development. Therefore, there is intense need of quality management in the educational sector especially at the basic level. The basic educational system acts as foundation stone for the academic future of every nation which is possible by ensuring principles of quality management of basic schools (Murad and Rajesh, 2010).

Total quality management (TQM) as a management approach of an organization which is concentrated on quality in which all its workforce are involved to ensure organizational development and long-term success. This aim could be possible through customer satisfaction. In addition to customer satisfaction, it is imperative to beneficialize the society and all the employees of an organization (Karani and Okibo, 2012).

TQM is an organized and systematic quality improvement approach for organizational management to improve its outcomes in terms of quality, customer satisfaction, production and profitability. As TQM has been adopted by many organizations world-wide for decades, therefore, it has captured the attention of many researchers from different areas (Gharakhani, et al, 2013).

The aim of total quality management is to utilize resources effectively, to accomplish success, and to ensure financial stability. Successful TQM implementation results in improving overall organizational performance such as improved employees participation, better communication and improved enrolment of learners, better quality and improved competitive advantage (Wani and Mehraj, 2014).

As Tichy and Cohen (2007) stressed that Total quality management is termed as management approach used to improve the quality, efficiency and productivity in organizations especially businesses. TQM is a broad system approach performing horizontally through an organization involving all departments and workers and extending backward and forward to include both suppliers and customers. This requires brilliant leadership staff, although they remain the scarcest resource in the world today.

TQM ensures to fulfill the needs as indicated by the customers. It is achieved through workforce in the organization being committed to achieve the targets or results, a desire for quality and decisions based on performance data (Kaufman (2002). TQM plays a crucial role in uplifting and ensuring long-term success of an organization. In addition, implementation of TQM has been considered an important factor for enhancing organizational productivity and efficiency according to Gharakhani, et al(2013).

Important elements for TQM implementation comprise of establishing a strong sense of school vision; improving personal mastery learning of workforce; concentrating on student-driven values; developing commendable and achievable goals; and enhancing day-to-day and routine management (Herman & Herman, 2005).

Commenting on TQM implementation, Toremén et al (2009) mentioned that there is need for an effective change management, educating staff and utilizing human resources to attain a system-wide quality improvement, to implement the principles of TQM. Successful implementation of TQM needs effective leadership, institutional commitment and a clear vision.

According to Wani and Mehraj (2014), the development of a long-range leadership, teamwork for a common vision and institutional commitment are necessary factors for the successful implementation of TQM. Further they added that leadership, accountability and cooperation are important dimensions of TQM which have positive effects on the organizational performance. Therefore, these dimensions of TQM may be implemented, improved, well-organized and made effective to ensure effective functioning, better performance and quality.

Yusuf et al. (2007) also stressed on effective leadership for successful implementation of TQM and mentioned that management leadership is a vital factor in implementing TQM because it ensures better performance through influencing workforce within an organization. Lack of commitment in the top management levels causes problems in successful TQM implementation. Top management is totally involved in implementing and stimulating the TQM approach. Further they added that effective implementation of TQM needs effective reforms in organizational environment and culture which is not possible without effective management and leadership. Effective leadership may promote a clear mission and then devise appropriate strategies to make it successful.

Effective management is an important and indispensable factor for the successful implementation of TQM. Commitment of top management assists the workforce to adopt a clear direction of functioning and working (Pheng and Jasmine, 2014). Other contributory factors regarding TQM implementation are; resources; employee satisfaction and needs; training; suitable organizational culture; favorable environment; subordinates' cooperation; effective curriculum; effective planning etc. which are essential to successful implementation of TQM.

Ater (2013) found that resources are very beneficial in the process of TQM implementation in public secondary schools. Personnel, educational materials and funding are very important for successful implementation of TQM. He commented on employee satisfaction and mentioned that recognition, appreciation and rewarding activities may promote and stimulate workforce commitment for quality improvement. Otherwise, these activities will be useless and lead to failure. Better working conditions; attractive salary packages; staff up gradation; financial rewards for better suggestions are excellent and effective techniques for appreciation, recognition and rewards. Further he mentioned that workers may be considered valuable and the resources may be utilized for their quality education and training throughout their career.

Discussing on the importance of training and development of workforce, Ater (2013) and Mann (2012) mentioned that training and development of personnel is one of the most important aspects of TQM implementation. Munro (2008) revealed that inadequate knowledge, lack of tools, lack of funding, lack of feasible leadership commitment, poor data and deployment plans, inflexibility of piecemeal implementation, unrealistic expectations, and inadequate managerial skills are some possible barriers in the process of successful implementation of TQM.

Lack of top management commitment affects TQM efforts negatively which is one of the main reasons of failure of TQM effort. Ineffective leadership; obstruction to change; contradictory policies; inappropriate organizational structure; and poor management of the change process are other shortcomings in implementing TQM (Dale, et al., 2007).

Kosgei (2014) concluded that a number of challenges in implementing TQM were; lack of commitment by the management and some workforce, school's organizational culture, poor documentation, inadequate training of staff, and ineffective communication.

In a research study conducted by Mobegi et al, (2010) they revealed that there were insufficient physical, learning and instructional materials in all schools. The ratio of textbook-pupil was 1:20. Furthermore, they reported that over 81.1% mixed boys and girls' schools lacked important facilities, such as tapped water, transport and electricity.

Hamidi and Zamanparrar (2008) investigated problems and barriers in implementing TQM and they reported that lack of senior and middle management commitment is the main barrier in implementing TQM. Lack of senior management commitment is an important factor that causes failure reports in implementing TQM. They further added that no progress is possible without management commitment and ensuring

appropriate and supportive organizational culture. Training programs for the workforce are essential for the effective TQM implementation.

Effective and successful total quality management (TQM) implementation can be a powerful vehicle by which organizations can achieve excellence in business performance (Ater, 2013). Implementation of total quality management (TQM) enables organizations to continuously improve quality of their products and service to meet and satisfy changing customer's needs. This takes place within a dynamic changing environment brought about by competition and demand for higher quality.

Total Quality Management used together is usually meant to recognize that real quality requires all elements of the institution to work together towards achieving the end. The concept of TQM is applicable to academics. Many educators believe that it provides guiding principles for needed educational reform. Students take classes, consume meals, sleep in residence halls, buy books and use many services for which they pay tuition other fees. The student certainly fits the definition of the word customer. Quality is an achievable measurable, profitable unit that can be achieved when one has the commitment and understanding and is prepared for the hard work.

According to Stella and Grynam, (2004) quality enhancement cannot be achieved as an administrative process. It is a participative process involving various units of the institution, at all levels is likely to bring new strains together with unprecedented possibilities. Life in the coming decades in educational institutions at all levels is likely to bring new strains together with unprecedented possibilities. To enable the people to benefit in the new environment will require new designs of human resource development. Many of the strategies of quality improvement in education are derived from industrial setting.

Academic institutions have used both the approaches in applying TQM in higher education settings. Quality of education takes into account external environment in which institutions operate: internal environment where teaching learning takes place and home environment of learners. The systems approach to education comprises of inputs, processes and outputs, all encompassed in an arbitrary boundary, and the environment. Inputs from its environment cross the boundary into the system: these are acted on within the transformation/production process and finally released from the system back into the environment as outputs. The direction of flow from the inputs, through transformation/ production process to the output indicates the flow of energy, information etc. Inputs are human, physical and financial resources, (students, faculty, administrators and organizational culture) Process is a series of actions or operations concluding to an end. A process transforms measurable inputs into measurable outputs under a value adding operation.

Each TQM initiative is unique, there are some common features. On the large canvas, TQM provides a direction and framework for morality in education. It considers and reward the effort of those directly involved, both inside and outside the organization. Successful TQM models tend to embody concepts of integrity, honesty, commitment, participation and ownership. By applying the various principles of TQM, the present school education can be improved and goal of quality education in schools can be achieved. There are a number of studies conducted in education which show the positive response of TQM in education in achieving the quality education. For quality school education, total quality must be the highest priority in the school. Everything should be quality focused. In educational institutions, highest priority should be given to quality education so that qualified learners can be produced. Quality definition should be clear. Any definition of quality must include satisfying the agreed learners needs and expectations.

Long term satisfaction of learners needs should be an aim of total quality organization. A total quality organization will communicate openly clearly its principles, mission and policy for quality. Communication at all levels will flow smoothly for better performance. The highest levels of integrity honesty, trust and openness are essential ingredients of Total Quality Management. Health, safety and environmental issues will have a high priority within a total quality organization for teaching and non-teaching staff and students. Grievance reduction cells, which will work round the clock for the learners to redress their grievances.

Quality circles are to be formed, which consists of small groups of people that meet on the regular basis to discuss problems to seek solutions and to cooperate with the management in the implementation of those solutions. Quality circles utilize organized approaches to problem solving and operate on the principle that employee participation in decision making and problem solving improves the quality of work. In education quality deals with monitoring and identifying the areas that affect the levels of teaching. Total Quality Management involves continuous measureable improvements at all levels of school, ranging from school performance to employee performance, so that continuous process improvement, forever, will become an essential ingredient of success.

B. School Performance

A strand of the literature measures school performance using teacher-based outcomes such as teachers' evaluations of school principal performance (Ballou and Podgursky, 2013) and teacher mobility/attrition (Gates et al., 2006). Teacher ratings can overcome some of the limitations of student based measures, to the extent that teachers are aware of factors such as the socio-economic background of the study body, but these evaluations are subjective, and may not be strongly related to student outcomes.

Performance could be described in various ways. It could be an act of accomplishing or executing a given task (Robert and Tim, 2008). It could also be described as the ability to combine skillfully the right behavior towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives (Olaniyan, 2009).

Performance is basically the ability of individual to use its knowledge efficiently and effectively. When researchers discuss the teacher's performance, it is based on both aspect the intellectual and physical. Brackett et al, (2006) studied the teacher's performance according to the teacher's activities regarding the writing on board, spelling, and its class room management. In regarding performance, they also identified the role of teachers in different three areas like as job skill, attitude toward job, and involvement in professional development. Basically the performance of the teachers is the effectiveness of teaching performance.

Performance of teachers mainly depends on the teacher characteristics such as knowledge base, sense of responsibility, and inquisitiveness; the student characteristics such as opportunity to learn, and academic work; the teaching factors such as lesson structure, and communication; the learning aspects such as involvement and success; and the classroom phenomena such as environment and climate, and organization and management. If the teachers take care of these factors, their performance can be enhanced to the optimum level (Rao and Kumar, 2007). Teacher entrance and exit examination scores, years of experience, advanced degrees, and teaching credentials are either not related to student achievement and ratings of teacher effectiveness.

Performance is the extent to which an employee accomplishes the tasks that make up his or her job. Performance can also be defined as a record of outcomes produced during a specific job, over a specific time. Performance refers to the amount of effort, initiative and absenteeism, maintenance of standards and commitment displayed by individuals while performing the job tasks. All organizations must face up to the challenge of how to evaluate, utilize and develop the skills and abilities of their employees to ensure that organizational goals are achieved and also to ensure that individuals gain as much satisfaction as possible from their jobs, while making effective contributions (Byars and Rue, 2006).

Thomason and La Paro (2010) found that a wider variety of teacher characteristics including education level, years of experience, job satisfaction, and professional organization membership predicted quality teacher child interactions for preschool classrooms while only professional organization membership predicted quality for toddler classrooms.

Higher levels of teacher education have also been related to early childhood teacher emotional support and behavior guidance specifically (de Kruif et al., 2010; Pianta et al., 2006). Determining other pathways to

teacher effectiveness, such as informal professional development activities, is necessary (Sheridan, Edwards, Marvin, & Knoche, 2009). In a meta-analysis of studies on teacher training, Fukkink and Lont (2007) found that in-service training as a professional development activity was an effective tool for improving teaching behaviors as well as child outcomes in early childhood classrooms.

Additionally, in a study of 30 toddler child care classrooms, Thomason and La Paro (2009) found moderate to high correlations between teacher membership in a professional organization and classroom emotional support and behavior guidance. Fuligni et al (2009) focusing on more informal kinds of teacher professional development activities have also shown similar results.

Peretemode (2006) argued that job performance is determined by the workers' level of participation in the day to day running of the organization. According to Okunola (2010) performance may be described as "an act of accomplishing or executing a given task". It could also be described as the ability to combine skillfully the right behavior towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives.

Obilade (2009) states that teachers job performance can be described as "the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. Okeniyi (2005) says that it could be described as "the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes". Peretemode (2006) adds that job performance is determined by the worker's level of participation in the day to day running of organization. There are some factors which contribute to teacher's performance. Clarifying the expectations that institutions and departments have for their faculty and that faculty had for their own performance are central to a successful faculty evaluation system. Expectations for faculty work responsibilities and outcomes are affected by institutional, departmental, disciplinary, and individual faculty priorities.

Challenges to the adoption and implementation of management concepts in educational institutions are several. One has to overcome the challenges to be able to take the best from industrial experiences and combine this in a holistic framework, with the methods more suited to the educational milieu. Issues of TQM should be addressed in educational institutions, particularly as they relate to productivity and financing. Those adopting TQM in education have varying perspectives on the approach. Some see TQM as a management system with customer or student satisfaction as the crucial element.

C. Conceptual framework

This study is hinged in the concept of total quality, introduced by Professor W. Edwards Deming in the 1950s, can be applied to almost every organization up to a certain level. The term stands for the process of shifting the focus of the organization towards a superior quality of products and services.

TQM approach in education involves not only achieving high quality but also influencing all segments of the educational process: organization, management, interpersonal relations, material and human resources, etc. Applying the approach described above quality becomes total (integral). The introduction of total quality management requires a number of changes in educational institutions. The first changes have to occur in the attitudes and activities of the management, in the organization and monitoring of the educational process, in the evaluation of its results, in the culture of communication, in the school atmosphere, and especially in the area of interpersonal relations.

The total quality management model includes the following: process planning, process management, continual improvement, total involvement and focus on the user. Total quality management is an efficient management technique that requires the full involvement of all employees on all organizational levels, thus representing the organizational culture. TQM stands for a way of life of the organization, which introduces constant improvement of business on all levels and activities, creating the appropriate environment through collaborative work, trust and respect. It approaches the processes in a systematic, consistent and organized way and applies total quality management techniques. TQM is all about quality management of the users,

leadership and management loyalty, and continuous improvement; prompt response, actions based on facts, the participation of employees in the TQM culture. If an organization is constantly willing to direct its efforts towards business improvement, the principles presented above can lead to excellence in quality. The success of total quality management depends on its eight components: ethics, integrity, trust, education, teamwork, leadership, recognizability and communication.

Total Quality Management (TQM) is a management approach that seeks to achieve and sustain long-term organizational success by encouraging employee feedback and participation, satisfying customer needs and expectations, respecting societal beliefs and values, and obeying governmental laws and regulations (Charantimath, 2003).

Another TQM definition that carries the same meaning was introduced by Corrigan (2005) who defined TQM as a "management philosophy that builds customer-driven learning organizations dedicated to total customer satisfaction through continuous improvement in the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization and its processes" (p. 61). According to Wilkinson and Witcher (1991), TQM is composed of three terms: Total: meaning that every person is involved including customer and suppliers, Quality: implying that customer requirements are met exactly and Management: indicating that senior executives are fully committed. TQM is more than a management philosophy; it can be considered a convenient framework used in and by organizations to guarantee a systematic and permanent optimization of the added value in order to maximize the realization of their aims. As a consequence of this proactive approach, all primary, supporting and managerial processes have to be designed in a manner that ensures an optimal (perceived) quality for customers, employees and other stakeholders (De Knop, Van Hoecke, & De Bosscher, 2004).

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the study. It shows the relationship between variables. The profile of the Adventist teachers and TQM implementation will be the independent the school performance will be the dependent variable.

Research Paradigm

Fig. 1: Schematic Diagram of the Study

CHAPTER 3

A. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the research method, locale of the study, the sampling procedure, and the respondents of the study, the instrumentation and the statistical technique used.

B. Research Method

The study will use the descriptive-correlational survey method to describe the profile of the teachers, level of Total Quality Management and school performance. The relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables will be determined.

C. Subjects of the Study

The participants of the study included the elementary teachers of Adventist schools of Bukidnon. There are 107 teachers of 20 Adventist schools in the province under North- Central Mindanao Conference.

Complete enumeration will be used to determine the sample size.

D. The Research Locale

The study will be conducted at Bukidnon Province. It is the eighth largest province in the country, is situated upon a landlocked plateau at the center of Northern Mindanao. It is bounded on the north and northwest by Misamis Oriental, on the east by Agusan del Sur and Davao del Norte, on the south by North Cotabato and on the west by the Lanao provinces. This will cover the 20 Adventist schools located in Bukidnon. . Figure 2 shows the location map of Bukidnon.

E. Instrumentation

The instrument of the study was adopted from Martin Barlosky and Professor Steve Lawton in their very useful *Developing Quality Schools* (1995) . This self-assessment has been devised specifically for education and incorporates key areas, such as teaching and learning and services to students that are lacking in the generic checklists.

In this self-assessment checklist there are 10 quality indicators: access; services to customers; leadership; physical environment and resources; effective learning and teaching; students; staff; external relations; organizations; and standards. These have been weighted to show their relative importance in the quality process. The highest weighted areas are effective teaching and learning and leadership. Leadership is of crucial importance because numerous studies have shown that strong leadership is a key feature of high performing educational institutions. Excellent leaders inspire their staff and ensure that there is a drive for quality improvement. In those establishments where student success is high, those working in them and particularly their management have a clear understanding of standards and the actions necessary to achieve them. Try out of questionnaire will be done to ensure validity and reliability of the instrument.

Fig. 2: Location Map of Bukidnon

F. Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher will seek permission from the Education Director of North Central Mindanao Conference through a request letter to conduct the research in all Adventist schools of Northern Mindanao. Upon the approval of the request, the questionnaires will be distributed to the Adventist teachers in their respective schools. The researcher will explain the general instructions before administering the questionnaires to the respondents.

G. Scoring Procedure

The scale and scoring below will be used to determine the extent of TQM implementation in the present study.

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

H. Statistical Techniques

Responses to the questionnaires and the data which will be collected will be summarized, translated and analyzed. The descriptive statistics will be employed for the summary and analysis of data including frequencies, percentage, and means.

The relationship between the independent variables will be established using the Pearson product Moment Correlation analysis.

One way ANOVA was used to find the significant difference between the independent and dependent variables.

CHAPTER 4

A. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

a) Demographic Profile of the Adventist Teachers

The demographic profile of the Adventist teachers is presented in Table 1.

CATEGORY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age		
• 25 years and below	36	29
• 26-35 years old	40	32.3
• 36-45 years old	28	22.6
• 46-55 years old	10	8.1
• 56-65 years old	10	8.1
Gender		
• Male	24	19.4
• Female	100	80.6
Civil Status		
• Single	34	27.4
• Married	86	69.4
• Separated	2	1.6
• Widowed	2	1.6
Educational attainment		
• Bachelor Degree	102	82.3
• Masteral Degree	18	14.5
• Doctoral Degree	4	3.2
Years in Service		
• 3 years and below	52	41.9
• 5-10 years	38	30.6
• 11-15 years	12	9.7
• 16-20 years	4	3.2
• 21-25 years	8	6.5
• 26-30 years	8	6.5

Table 1: Demographic profile of the Adventist teachers

There were 40 (32.3%) teachers who have an age range of 26-35 years old. Followed with 36(29%) teachers who are 25 years and below; Majority of them were female (100, 80.6%). There are 86 (69.4%) married; 34 (27.4%). For the educational attainment, Out of 124 teachers, 102 of them are bachelor degree holder; 18 attained Masteral degree, and 4 doctoral degree holder. Almost half of the teachers or 52 of them worked for 3 years and below. Followed with 38 teachers who are in service for 5 -10 years.

b) Level of Total Quality Management Implementation in Adventist Schools

There were 10 subscales in the level of implementation of Total Quality Management of Adventist schools in Bukidnon. The quality indicators included were: access; services to customers; leadership; physical environment and resources; effective learning and teaching; students; staff; external relations; organizations; and standards.

Table 2: Access as quality indicator of TQM

Quality Indicators	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
Access		
1. There is a welcoming reception.	4.09	Moderately implemented
2. There is a clear initial contact point for all customers.	3.95	Moderately implemented
3. Advice and guidance facilities are readily available.	3.77	Moderately implemented
4. There are clear signs around the campus.	3.51	Moderately implemented
5. Signs and literature are produced in community languages.	3.51	Moderately implemented
6. Telephone response times are short.	3.35	Unsure
7. There are appropriate ramps and lifts for people with disabilities	3.08	Unsure
Overall mean	3.60	Moderately Implemented

Table 2: Showed the quality indicators in terms of access; There were 7 constructs.

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

The top 3 indicators were: There is a welcoming reception with a mean of 4.09; there is a clear initial contact point for all customers (3.95); and Advice and guidance facilities are readily available with a mean of 3.77 which is described as moderately implemented.

On the other hand, the least rated indicators were: There are appropriate ramps and lifts for people with disabilities with a mean of 3.08; and telephone response time are short (3.35). The overall mean for access is 3.60 which is described as moderately implemented.

The findings of the study implied that Adventist schools have reception area to welcome their visitors, advice and guidance facilities are available for counseling while the teachers were unsure on the appropriate ramps and lifts for persons with disabilities, and communication system such as telephones. It can be observed that Adventist schools in Bukidnon lacked appropriate facilities to aid persons with disability and limited telephone services.

Table 3 revealed the services to customers' quality indicators. There were 12 constructs under this subscale.

Services to customers	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. Appropriate continuing guidance is available to all students.	4.08	Moderately Implemented
2. There are opportunities for students to organize their own activities.	4.04	Moderately Implemented
3. Effective pre-entry guidance is available for all students.	3.90	Moderately Implemented
4. Accessible student welfare and counseling is available to all students who need it.	3.83	Moderately Implemented
5. Affordable canteen facilities are available when students require them.	3.83	Moderately Implemented
6. An effective information and guidance service is available.	3.77	Moderately Implemented
7. Adequate sports facilities are available.	3.67	Moderately Implemented
8. Appropriate relaxation facilities are available	3.64	Moderately Implemented
9. Careers guidance is readily available.	3.56	Moderately Implemented
10. Open-access to learning resources is available to all students.	3.50	Unsure
11. Open-access computer facilities are available to all students.	3.48	Unsure
12. A well- resourced library and resource center is available with appropriate resources to meet curriculum needs.	3.29	Unsure
Overall mean	3.71	Moderately Implemented

Table 3: Services to customers quality indicators

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

It can be observed that most of the indicators were perceived as moderately implemented. The top 3 indicators include: Appropriate continuing guidance is available to all students (4.08); There are opportunities for students to organize their own activities (4.04); and effective pre-entry guidance is available for all students (3.90) while there were indicators which the teachers were unsure of: A well-resourced library and resource center is available with appropriate resources to meet curriculum needs (3.29); Open-access computer facilities are available to all students (3.48); and open – access to learning

resources is available to all students. The overall mean is 3.71 which is described as moderately implemented.

The findings implied that Adventist schools in Bukidnon lack in a well-resourced library; resource center; and computer facilities to serve their students.

Leadership of Head / Principal Quality indicators were presented in Table 4. There were 9 constructs in this sub variable. All indicators were perceived as moderately implemented.

LEADERSHIP Head/Principal	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. He/she knows the students.	4.48	Moderately Implemented
2. He/ she know the staff.	4.45	Moderately Implemented
3. He/she walks the job.	4.30	Moderately Implemented
4. He/she leads innovation and creativity	4.22	Moderately Implemented
5. He/she gives top priority to quality improvement	4.19	Moderately Implemented
6. He/she provides leadership	4.17	Moderately Implemented
7. He/she has a vision and shares it.	4.12	Moderately Implemented
8. He/she ensures that quality champions are in place.	4.01	Moderately Implemented
9. He/ she champion the message of TQM.	4.00	Moderately Implemented
Overall mean	4.21	Moderately implemented

Governance

1. There is a strong commitment to the needs of the community.	4.43	Moderately Implemented
2. The institution's mission and ethos is clear and understood by staff, students and the community.	4.30	Moderately Implemented
3. Ensures that the institution has a framework for quality improvement in place.	4.12	Moderately Implemented
4. The Board/ Trustees effectively monitor the quality of provision, including the major indicators of success in student recruitment.	4.09	Moderately Implemented
5. The Board/trustees works with the Head/Principal to develop the institution's mission.	4.08	Moderately Implemented

6. The Board/ Trustees effectively monitors' the quality of provision, including the major indicators of success of student achievement.	4.06	Moderately Implemented
7. An equal opportunities policy is in place and implemented.	4.04	Moderately Implemented
8. The Board/ Trustees effectively monitor the quality of provision, including the major indicators of success in self-assessment report and action plan.	3.95	Moderately Implemented
9. The Board/ Trustees effectively monitor the quality of provision, including the major indicators of success in financial solvency.	3.91	Moderately Implemented
10. The Board/ Trustees effectively monitor the quality of provision, including the major indicators of success in student retention.	3.83	Moderately Implemented
Overall mean	4.08	Moderately Implemented

Table 4: Leadership quality indicators in terms of Head/Principal and governance

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

The teachers perceived that the principal knows the students (4.48); knows the staffs (4.45); and walks the job (4.30). The overall mean is 4.21 and described as moderately implemented.

For the governance, the overall mean is 4.08; all indicators were perceived as moderately implemented. There is a strong commitment to the needs of the community (4.43); The institution's mission and ethics is clear and understood by staff, students, and the community (4.30); and ensures that the institution has a framework for quality improvement in place (4.12).

The findings of the study implied that the leadership of principal and governance is moderately implemented in the Adventist schools of Bukidnon. It can be observed that the principals have active interactions with the teachers and students in their respective schools.

Among the quality indicators under physical environment and resources, the teachers perceived all indicators as moderately implemented. It can be seen that the classroom contain appropriate visual aids and learning aids (4.27); There is a strong commitment to maintaining a safe and secure environment (4.22); and classroom layouts/ individual learning programs are exciting to students (4.20); and The buildings are clean and attractive (4.09). The findings of the study implied that the physical environment improvement is moderately implemented. Classroom visual aids are visible in every classroom of Adventist schools in Bukidnon.

Ater (2013) found that resources are very beneficial in the process of TQM implementation in public secondary schools. Personnel, educational materials and funding are very important for successful

implementation of TQM. He commented on employee satisfaction and mentioned that recognition, appreciation and rewarding activities may promote and stimulate workforce.

Physical environment and resources	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
	4.27	Moderately implemented
1. Classroom contains appropriate visual aids and learning aids.		
2. There is a strong commitment to maintaining a safe and secure environment.	4.22	Moderately implemented
3. Classroom layouts/ individual learning programs are exciting to students.	4.20	Moderately implemented
4. The buildings are clean and attractive.	4.09	Moderately implemented
5. Quality costs are regularly monitored and reported.	4.09	Moderately implemented
6. The facilities are fit for purpose.	4.08	Moderately implemented
7. The learning environments are well-planned and organized.	4.06	Moderately implemented
8. Student perception/ incident logs are kept.	4.04	Moderately implemented
9. Effective resource control is exercised.	4.04	Moderately implemented
10. Health and safety policies are regularly monitored	4.01	Moderately implemented
11. There is appropriate delegation of resource management.	4.00	Moderately implemented
12. The institution has a clear idea of the costs of quality failures	4.00	Moderately implemented
13. Resources are controlled by those who use them.	3.85	Moderately implemented
Overall mean	4.07	Moderately implemented

Table 5: Physical environment and resources quality indicators

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

Commitment for quality improvement. Otherwise, these activities will be useless and lead to failure. Better working conditions; attractive salary packages; staff up gradation; financial rewards for better suggestions are excellent and effective techniques for appreciation, recognition and rewards. Further he mentioned that workers may be considered valuable and the resources may be utilized for their quality education and training throughout their career.

Table 6 revealed the effective learning and teaching quality indicators of TQM. There were 15 constructs in this sub-variable.

Effective learning and teaching	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. Student feedback is regularly obtained	4.50	Moderately implemented
2. Students are encouraged to take responsibility for their own learning.	4.48	Moderately implemented
3. There is a good climate of purposefulness among students.	4.48	Moderately implemented
4. The content of programs is relevant and up to date.	4.48	Moderately implemented
5. There is a recognition of prior learning	4.45	Moderately implemented
6. The curriculum is appropriate to learners' needs	4.45	Moderately implemented
7. Learning is student centered.	4.38	Moderately implemented
8. Student and community questionnaire are used where appropriate.	4.38	Moderately implemented
9. There are teaching and learning strategies appropriate to course and program goals.	4.27	Moderately implemented
10. Teaching and learning strategies are measured by student response.	4.27	Moderately implemented
11. A variety of learning modes are available to meet learner's need.	4.22	Moderately implemented
12. Teaching and learning strategies are regularly reviewed and measured by a range of specified criteria.	4.04	Moderately implemented
13. The institution has formal systems for review and evaluation	4.04	Moderately implemented
14. There is evidence that student feedback is used in policy making.	3.85	Moderately implemented
15. Feedback from other customer groups is regularly obtained.	3.43	Unsure
Overall mean	4.24	Moderately implemented

Table 6: Effective Learning and Teaching quality indicators

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

The top rated indicators were: student feedback is regularly obtained (4.50); students are encouraged to take responsibility for their own learning and there is a good climate of purposefulness among

students with a mean of 4.8 respectively which is described as moderately implemented while one indicator was perceived as unsure: feedback from customer groups is regularly obtained (3.43). Overall, effective learning and teaching is moderately implemented with a mean of 4.24.

The findings implied that students' feedback and the school climate are moderately implemented. Adventist schools in Bukidnon lacked feedback from their customer groups such as the parents, stakeholders and etc.

Quality indicators for students are found in Table 7. There were 13 constructs in this sub-variable. There were 2 indicators which were perceived by the teachers as extremely implemented in Adventist schools in Bukidnon. Students' attendance is regularly monitored with a mean of 4.53 and there is a good rapport between staff and students with a mean of 4.51 while the top 3 indicators rated as moderately implemented are the following: Students' progress is regularly tracked and monitored (4.43); students are kept informed about developments that affects them (4.41); and Tutorial provision is used effectively to ensure that students are on track (4.37). The overall mean for students indicator is 4.22 which is described as moderately implemented.

Students	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. Students' attendance is regularly monitored and tracked	4.53	Extremely implemented
2. There is a good rapport between staff and students.	4.51	Extremely implemented
3. Students' progress is regularly tracked and monitored.	4.43	Moderately implemented
4. Students are kept informed about developments that affect them.	4.41	Moderately implemented
5. Tutorial provision is used effectively to ensure that students are on track.	4.37	Moderately implemented
6. Happy students and satisfied customers are evidenced through surveys and questionnaires.	4.29	Moderately implemented
7. Students' views are regularly solicited.	4.16	Moderately implemented
8. There are good range of leisure, recreation and sporting facilities available to students.	4.14	Moderately implemented
9. Student handbooks and guides are available.	4.03	Moderately implemented
10. Student has a sense of pride in their work.	4.03	Moderately implemented
11. The communal areas are clean and well-decorated.	4.01	Moderately implemented
12. There are good transport arrangements for students.	4.01	Moderately implemented
13. There is an absence of artificial barriers	3.95	Moderately implemented
Overall mean	4.22	Moderately implemented

Table 7: Student's quality indicators

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

Table 8 reflected the staff quality indicators of Total Quality Management. There were 17 constructs about this sub-variable.

Staff	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. Staffs are committed and knowledgeable.	4.59	Extremely implemented
2. Staffs take responsibility for their own quality.	4.59	Extremely implemented
3. Staffs readily respond to individual needs.	4.56	Extremely implemented
4. Staff have a sense of enjoyment in their work	4.51	Extremely implemented
5. Staff have a student – centered approach	4.48	Moderately implemented
6. There is a commitment to teamwork and team approaches	4.43	Moderately implemented
7. Staff are trained in the skills of teamwork	4.37	Moderately implemented
8. The institution is committed to developing its staff	4.33	Moderately implemented
9. Staff have strong cohesion	4.29	Moderately implemented
10. There is a resource base that allows them to improve quality	4.25	Moderately implemented
11. Teams are regularly consulted on policy.	4.21	Moderately implemented
12. The institution is proactive and clearly states institutional needs.	4.20	Moderately implemented
13. Staffs are trained in quality improvement techniques.	4.14	Moderately implemented
14. Staff training is an institutional priority.	4.01	Moderately implemented
15. Staff training is adequately resourced and funded.	3.96	Moderately implemented
16. There are adequate and appropriate equipment and facilities.	3.88	Moderately implemented
17. There is a good staff workrooms	3.82	Moderately implemented
Overall mean	4.27	Moderately implemented

Table 8: Staff quality indicators

Legend

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

There were 5 indicators which are being extremely implemented in the Adventist schools of Bukidnon. These were: Staff are committed and knowledgeable and Staff take responsibility for their own quality with a mean of 4.59 respectively. Followed by staff readily respond to individual needs (4.56); Staff have a sense of enjoyment in their work (4.51); and Staff have a student-centered approach (4.48).

On the other hand, the least rated indicators include: there is a good staff workrooms (3.82); there are adequate and appropriate equipment and facilities (3.88); and staff training is adequately resourced and funded (3.96) which were described as moderately implemented.

The findings implied that Adventist school teachers are committed and upheld quality education to their students by established student-centered approach but some factors were being identified as the schools lacked good staff workrooms, and adequate appropriate equipment and facilities.

External quality indicators were discussed in Table 9. All 7 indicators were perceived as moderately implemented. It can be observed that the institution is positively seeking out customer views (4.11); There are strong links with community agencies through partnerships(4.03); and community views are regularly solicited (3.93). Overall, the external indicators were moderately implemented with a mean of 3.91.

External relations	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. The institution is positively seeking out customer views.	4.11	Moderately implemented
2. There are strong links with community agencies through partnerships.	4.03	Moderately implemented
3. Community views are regularly solicited.	3.93	Moderately implemented
4. Excellent links with relevant communities are maintained	3.91	Moderately implemented
5. There is a coherent marketing strategy.	3.88	Moderately implemented
6. Market research is regularly carried out	3.77	Moderately implemented
7. Student and employer questionnaires are regularly used.	3.74	Moderately implemented
Overall mean	3.91	Moderately implemented

Table 9: External quality indicators

Legend

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

Table 10 showed the organization quality indicators. There were 14 indicators in this sub-variable. The top rated indicators were: staff at all levels are aware of the institution's direction (4.30); Mutuality in communication is seen as the lifeblood of the institution (4.25); and the institution's managers are committed to quality improvement (4.24).

Organization	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. Staff at all levels are aware of the institution's direction	4.30	Moderately implemented
2. Mutuality in communication is seen as the lifeblood of the institution.	4.25	Moderately implemented
3. The institution's managers are committed to quality improvement.	4.24	Moderately implemented
4. There is a universal statement of direction.	4.24	Moderately implemented
5. The institution has broad aims and objectives	4.22	Moderately implemented
6. Communications are bottom-up not just top-down.	4.20	Moderately implemented
7. The plan identifies how staff can contribute to success.	4.19	Moderately implemented
8.		
9. The institution has a simple and lean organizational structure.	4.19	Moderately implemented
10. Authority is delegated down.	4.19	Moderately implemented
11. The organization is prefaced upon teamwork.	4.19	Moderately implemented
12. Good communications are seen as a major priority	4.17	Moderately implemented
13. The institution has a written strategic plan	4.09	Moderately implemented
14. There is a policy in place for effectively using the institution's knowledge resources.	4.08	Moderately implemented
15. A range of quality tools and techniques is used to improve quality.	3.48	Unsure
Overall mean	4.14	Moderately implemented

Table 10: Organization quality indicators

Legend

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

On the other hand, one indicator was perceived as unsure which is “a range of quality tools and techniques is used to improve quality (3.48). The overall mean is 4.14 which are described as moderately implemented.

Table 11 showed the Standards quality indicators. There were 10 constructs in this sub variable. Student welfare is a priority is extremely implemented while the rest of the indicators were moderately implemented. The overall mean for standards is 4.24 which is described as moderately implemented.

Standards	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. Student welfare is a priority.	4.51	Extremely implemented
2. There is a commitment to learners of all abilities	4.46	Moderately implemented
3. There is a welcoming environment	4.43	Moderately implemented
4. There is a caring atmosphere	4.40	Moderately implemented
5. Customer service is in evidence	4.32	Moderately implemented
6. The institution has excellent exam results and student successes.	4.09	Moderately implemented
7. The institution has high progression rates for students obtaining appropriate employment or places in other educational institutions.	4.08	Moderately implemented
8. The institution has high student retention rates.	4.06	Moderately implemented
9. There is effective budgetary control.	4.06	Moderately implemented
10. Good student and community feedback based on systematic data collection is obtained.	4.04	Moderately implemented
Overall mean	4.24	Moderately implemented

Table 11: Standards quality indicators

Legend

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

The level of Total Quality Management implementation of Adventists schools in Bukidnon is shown in Table 12. It can be seen that the overall mean is 4.05 which is described as “moderately implemented”.

The findings implied that Adventist schools practiced and implemented the TQM indicators in their respective schools but some of the indicators were not fully implemented.

QUALITY INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. Access	3.60	Moderately implemented
2. Services to customers	3.71	Moderately implemented
3. Leadership	4.14	Moderately implemented
4. Physical environment and resources.	4.07	Moderately implemented
5. Effective learning and teaching	4.24	Moderately implemented
6. Students	4.22	Moderately implemented
7. Staff	4.27	Moderately implemented
8. External relations	3.91	Moderately implemented
9. Organizations	4.14	Moderately implemented
10. Standards	4.24	Moderately implemented
Overall mean	4.05	Moderately implemented

Table 12: Summary of TQM level of implementation in Adventist schools

Legend:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51-5.00	Extremely implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Unsure
2	1.50- 2.51	Slightly implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not at all implemented

Wani and Mehraj (2014), the development of a long-range leadership, teamwork for a common vision and institutional commitment are necessary factors for the successful implementation of TQM. Further they added that leadership, accountability and cooperation are important dimensions of TQM which have positive effects on the organizational performance. Therefore, these dimensions of TQM may be implemented, improved, well-organized and made effective to ensure effective functioning, better performance and quality.

Yusuf et al. (2007) also stressed on effective leadership for successful implementation of TQM and mentioned that management leadership is a vital factor in implementing TQM because it ensures better performance through influencing workforce within an organization. Lack of commitment in the top management levels causes problems in successful TQM implementation. Top management is totally involved in implementing and stimulating the TQM approach. Further they added that effective implementation of TQM needs effective reforms in organizational environment and culture which is not possible without effective management and leadership. Effective leadership may promote a clear mission and then devise appropriate strategies to make it successful.

Table 13 showed the school performance of Adventist schools in Bukidnon. Evaluations of the schools are done annually. The Department of Education Director of North –Central Mindanao Conference headed the team in doing the school evaluation. The schools have a performance rate of 91.85% which is described as Very Satisfactory.

(N=20)	Performance Percentage	Descriptive rating
Adventist Schools (Bukidnon)	91.85	Very Satisfactory

Table 13: School performance of Adventist schools in Bukidnon

Legend:

Range	Descriptive rating
96-100	Outstanding
90-95	Very Satisfactory
80-89	Satisfactory
75-79	Unsatisfactory
74 and below	Poor

VARIABLES	COEFFICIENT CORRELATION (r)	Sig.	Remarks
Profile of Teachers			
Age	.276	.239	Not Significant
Sex	.351	.129	Not Significant
Civil status	-.068	.776	Not Significant
Educational attainment	-.195	.411	Not Significant
Years in service	.287	.220	Not Significant
Level of TQM implementation			Not Significant
Access	.586	.167	Not Significant
Services to customers	-.051	.875	Not Significant
Leadership			
Head/ Principal	.034	.932	Not Significant
Governance	-.289	.418	Not Significant
Physical environment and resources.	-.193	.548	Not Significant
Effective learning and teaching	-.098	.729	Not Significant
Students	-.070	.820	Not Significant
Staff	.472	.056	Not Significant
External relations	-.731	.062	Not Significant
Organizations	.368	.195	Not Significant
Standards	-.590	.410	Not Significant

Table 14: Correlation between school performance, profile and level of TQM implementation

Correlations between variables are revealed Table 14. It can be gleaned that among the variables presented, the p value of the variables is greater than the level of significance of .05 . therefore, there is no significant relationship between the profile , TQM implementation and school performance of the Adventist schools in Bukidnon. This means that the profile of teachers, quality indicators of Total Quality Management do not affect the school performance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

VARIABLES	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Access						
Between Groups	.571	4	.143	1.69	.404	Not significant
Within Groups	.169	2	.084	2		
Services to customers						
Between Groups	.187	7	.027	.248	.948	Not significant
Within Groups	.430	4	.107			
Head/principal						
Between Groups	.088	6	.015	.203	.946	Not significant
Within Groups	.145	2	.072			
Governance	.129	6	.021	.540	.762	Not significant
Between Groups	.119	3	.040			
Within Groups						
Physical environment	.105	7	.015	1.54	.353	Not significant
Between Groups	.039	4	.010			
Within Groups						
Effective learning and teaching	.302	9	.034	.420	.878	Not significant
Between Groups	.400	5	.080			
Within Groups						
Students	.499	8	.062	7.78	.032	significant
Between Groups	.032	4	.058	5		
Within Groups						
Staff	.568	9	.063	1.08	.467	Not significant
Between Groups	.406	7	.058	7		
Within Groups						
External relations						
Between Groups	.088	4	.022	2.66	.291	Not significant
Within Groups	.016	2	.008	4		
Organization						
Between Groups	.072	9	.008	2.82	.165	Not significant
Within Groups	.011	4	.003	9		
Standards	.270	6	.045	1.86	.326	Not significant
Between Groups	.072	3	.024	0		
Within Groups						

Table 15: Difference between TQM quality indicators and school performance

Table 15 shows the difference between TQM implementation and school performance. It can be seen that majority of the TQM indicators are not statistically significant since the p value is greater than .05 level of significance.

On the other hand, There was a significant effect of students on the school performance ($F= 7.785$, p value= .032. Null hypothesis is rejected.

The concepts formulated by TQM founder, W. Edwards Deming, have been suggested as a basis for achieving excellence in schools. It is based on the assumption that people want to do their best and that it is management's job to enable them to do so by constantly improving the system in which they work. It requires teamwork, training, and extensive collection and analysis of data. It is an opportunity to conceptualize a systematic change for Adventist schools.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter contains the summary of findings, the conclusions extracted from the given findings, and the recommendations based on the conclusions.

A. Summary

The study determined the total quality management of Adventist education in the North-Central Mindanao Conference in the school year 2016–2017. It covered the 20 Adventist schools in Bukidnon. The study participants were 124 Adventist elementary school teachers who participated in the study.

TQM quality indicators include: access; services to customers; leadership; physical environment and resources; effective learning and teaching; students; staff; external relations; organizations; and standards.

School performance was based on the annual evaluation done by the Education Department of the North-Central Mindanao Conference. The study utilized the descriptive-correlative design. A survey questionnaire was used to gather reliable data from the respective schools. Findings revealed that most of the teachers have an age range of 26–35 years old. The majority of them are married with bachelor's degree holders. Almost half of them worked for 3 years or less.

The top 3 indicators of access were: there is a welcoming reception with a mean of 4.09; there is a clear initial contact point for all customers (3.95); and advice and guidance facilities are readily available with a mean of 3.77, which is described as moderately implemented. The least rated indicators were: there are appropriate ramps and lifts for people with disabilities, with a mean of 3.08; and telephone response time is short (3.35). The overall mean for access is 3.60, which is described as moderately implemented.

Most of the indicators of services to customers were perceived as moderately implemented. The top 3 indicators include: appropriate continuing guidance is available to all students (4.08); there are opportunities for students to organize their own activities (4.04); and effective pre-entry guidance is available for all students (3.90); while there were indicators which the teachers were unsure of: A well-resourced library and resource center are available with appropriate resources to meet curriculum needs (3.29); open-access computer facilities are available to all students (3.48); and open-access to learning resources is available to all students. The overall mean is 3.71, which is described as moderately implemented.

Leadership of Head/Principal Quality indicators were perceived as moderately implemented. The teachers perceived that the principal knows the students (4.48), knows the staff (4.45), and walks the job (4.30). The overall mean is 4.21 and is described as moderately implemented. For governance, the overall mean is 4.08; all indicators were perceived as moderately implemented. There is a strong commitment to the needs of the community (4.43); the institution's mission and ethics are clear and understood by staff, students, and the community (4.30); and ensures that the institution has a framework for quality improvement in place (4.12).

Among the quality indicators under physical environment and resources, the teachers perceived all indicators as moderately implemented. It can be seen that the classroom contains appropriate visual aids and learning aids (4.27); there is a strong commitment to maintaining a safe and secure environment (4.22); and classroom layouts/individual learning programs are exciting to students (4.20); and the buildings are clean and attractive (4.09).

The top rated indicators for effective learning and teaching were: student feedback is regularly obtained (4.50); students are encouraged to take responsibility for their own learning; and there is a good climate of purposefulness among students, with a mean of 4.8, which is described as moderately implemented, while

one indicator was perceived as unsure: feedback from customer groups is regularly obtained (3.43). Overall, effective learning and teaching are moderately implemented, with a mean of 4.24.

Quality indicators for students were perceived by the teachers as extremely implemented in Adventist schools in Bukidnon. Students' attendance is regularly monitored with a mean of 4.53 and there is a good rapport between staff and students with a mean of 4.51, while the top 3 indicators rated as moderately implemented are the following: Students' progress is regularly tracked and monitored (4.43); students are kept informed about developments that affect them (4.41); and tutorial provision is used effectively to ensure that students are on track (4.37). The overall mean for the student indicator is 4.22, which is described as moderately implemented. There were five indicators in the staff indicator which are being implemented extremely well in the Adventist schools of Bukidnon. These were: staff are committed and knowledgeable; and staff take responsibility for their own quality, with a mean of 4.59, respectively. Followed by staff readily responding to individual needs (4.56); staff having a sense of enjoyment in their work (4.51); and staff having a student-centered approach (4.48). The least rated indicators include: there are good staff workrooms (3.82); there is adequate and appropriate equipment and facilities (3.88); and staff training is adequately resourced and funded (3.96), which were described as moderately implemented.

External quality indicators were perceived as moderately implemented. The institution is positively seeking out customer views (4.11); there are strong links with community agencies through partnerships (4.03); and community views are regularly solicited (3.93). Overall, the external indicators were moderately implemented, with a mean of 3.91.

In the organization, the top-rated indicators were: staff at all levels are aware of the institution's direction (4.30); mutuality in communication is seen as the lifeblood of the institution (4.25); and the institution's managers are committed to quality improvement (4.24). One indicator was perceived as unsure, which means "a range of quality tools and techniques are used to improve quality (3.48). The overall mean is 4.14, which is described as moderately implemented.

Student welfare is a priority and is extremely implemented, while the rest of the indicators are moderately implemented. The overall mean for standards is 4.24, which is described as moderately implemented.

The level of Total Quality Management implementation of Adventist schools in Bukidnon is moderately implemented, with an overall mean of 4.05. The school performance of Adventist schools in Bukidnon has a performance rate of 91.85%, which is described as very satisfactory.

There is no significant relationship between the profiles and TQM implementation with regard to school performance.

The majority of the TQM indicators are not statistically significant since the p value is greater than the .05 level of significance. There was a significant difference in student performance at school ($F = 7.785$, $p \text{ value} = .032$).

B. Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of the study:

Most of the teachers have an age range of 26–35 years old. The majority of them are married with bachelor's degree holders. Almost half of them worked for 3 years or less.

The level of Total Quality Management implementation among Adventist schools in Bukidnon is "moderately implemented."

The school performance rating of the Adventist schools in Bukidnon is very satisfactory.

The null hypothesis is accepted since there is no significant relationship between the variables.

There is a significant difference between student variables and school performance; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

C. Recommendations

Based on the conclusions given, the following are then advanced for consideration.

Adventist school teachers are encouraged to upgrade their professional development through master's and doctoral schooling.

In TQM implementation, several indicators need to be implemented in all Adventist schools. The school must consider the appropriate designs of ramps and other facilities for people with disabilities.

The communication system must be functional to establish links among the students, parents, the community, and other stakeholders.

A well-resourced library and resource center must be implemented in each school. Computer facilities must be made available to the students.

Feedback from the customer groups, such as parents and other stakeholders, must be obtained regularly from the customer groups. A survey questionnaire can be utilized to gain feedback.

Staff workrooms must be available in the school so that teachers will have a good atmosphere to work in.

Allocation of resources and funds for staff training must be implemented in the schools so that teachers can participate in the training provided for them.

Quality tools and techniques to improve the school must be established so that continuous quality checking can be done so that indicators that need improvement will be developed and addressed positively.

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